

Funded by
the European Union

D7.1 PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY, WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ACCOUNTS

31/08/2024

Author:
Quentin Morel (TEN)

Funded by the European Union (Grant n°.101147094) Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority (CINEA) can be held responsible for them.

PROJECT GENERAL INFORMATION

Project Acronym	SOLVE
Project Title	Advancing SOLid-state battery development and production to driVE the future of electromobility
Grant Agreement Number	101147094
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02
Project Coordinator	Fundación CIDETEC
Project Duration	01 June 2024 – 31 May 2028 (48 months)

DELIVERABLE GENERAL INFORMATION

Deliverable No.	D7.1 Project visual identity, website and social networks accounts
Dissemination level	PU
Work Package	WP7
Task	T7.1 – Dissemination & Communication strategy
Lead beneficiary	TENERRDIS (TEN)
Reviewers	Amandeep Singh (TAU) Akshayan Sudharshan (PVS)
Date of deliverable	31/08/2024

DOCUMENT HISTORY

v	Date	Summary of Main Changes
1.0	25/07/2024	Initial version
2.0	01/08/2024	Integrated feedback from A. Singh / A. Sudharshan
3.0	28/08/2024	Integrated feedback from E. Sedano (CID)
4.0	29/08/2024	Final version in the official SOLVE template

Table of contents

PROJECT GENERAL INFORMATION	2
DELIVERABLE GENERAL INFORMATION	2
DOCUMENT HISTORY	2
LISTS	4
LIST OF FIGURES	4
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. THE BASICS	6
1.1. THE LOGO	6
1.2. COLOUR VARIATIONS	6
1.3. THE PROTECION ZONE	7
1.4. MINIMUM SIZE	8
1.5. RULES OF USE	8
1.6. PROHIBITIONS	9
1.7. POSITIONING THE LOGO	10
2. LEGAL OBLIGATIONS	15
2.1. VISIBILITY — EUROPEAN FLAG AND FUNDING STATEMENT	15
2.2. QUALITY OF INFORMATION — DISCLAIMER	17
3. THE GRAPHIC UNIVERSE	17
3.1. TYPOGRAPHY	17
3.2. COLOURS	18
3.3. SHAPES	19
3.4. ICONOGRAPHY	20
4. SOME EXAMPLES OF USE	21

5. THE WEBSITE	23
5.1. THE MOCK-UP	23
5.2. THE DIFFERENT SECTIONS	25
5.2.1. THE HOME PAGE	25
5.2.2. PROJECT	25
5.2.3. CONSORTIUM	25
5.2.4. NEWS	25
5.2.5. RESULTS	25
5.2.6. CONTACT	25
5.2.7. RESOURCES	25
6. SOCIAL MEDIA	26
6.1. LINKEDIN	26
6.2. X	28
6.3. YOUTUBE	28
CONCLUSIONS	29
ANNEX 1: COMMUNICATION PRODUCTION TIMELINE	30
ANNEX 2: REFERENCES	31

LISTS

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: SOLVE logo.....	6
Figure 2: Background colour preferences for SOLVE logo.....	7
Figure 3: Protection zone for SOLVE logo.....	7
Figure 4: Minimum size for SOLVE logo.....	8
Figure 5: Rules of use for SOLVE logo background.....	9
Figure 6: Prohibitions for SOLVE logo.....	9
Figure 7: Format: A4 (portrait) and homothetic (Size 1).....	10
Figure 8: Format: A4 (portrait) and homothetic (Size 2).....	11
Figure 9: Format: A4 (landscape) and homothetic (size 1).....	12
Figure 10: Format: A4 (landscape) and homethic (size 2).....	13
Figure 11: Format: kakemono, 85 x 200 cm.....	14
Figure 12: Co-funded European Union logos preferences.....	15
Figure 13: Funded European Union logos preferences.....	16
Figure 14: Protection area.....	16
Figure 15: Fractul typography.....	18
Figure 16: Arial typography.....	18

Figure 17: charter colours.....	19
Figure 18: Charter shapes.....	19
Figure 19: Examples of photos.....	20
Figure 20: Two-colour photographic.....	20
Figure 21: Stationery.....	21
Figure 22: Press release.....	21
Figure 23: Power point presentations.....	22
Figure 24: Website homepage.....	23
Figure 25: Website news.....	24
Figure 26: Website results.....	24
Figure 27: Website footer.....	24
Figure 28: The LinkedIn page.....	26
Figure 29: Examples of posts.....	27
Figure 30: The X page.....	28
Figure 31: The YouTube page.....	28
Figure 32: Communication production timeline.....	30

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
TAU	Tampere University
PVS	Pipistrel Vertical Solutions

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this document is to present the graphic identity of the SOLVE project, its graphic universe and the first communication tools: the website and social networks. It should be noted that this document is separate from the 'Communication & Dissemination Plan' which will be published on 30 November 2024 and for which this document serves as a support.

The goal of this document is to present the graphic universe that has been created by the Bastille communication agency for the SOLVE project. The document also mentions the obligations in the use of this graphic charter in order to maintain consistency and the restrictions to avoid any use that could damage the project's brand image.

This document was created while the graphic universe is still being developed. It outlines potential perspectives and use cases but does not fully represent what the final tools will look like.

The document will be updated and shared between project partners if necessary.

1. THE BASICS

The aim of this chapter is to present the logo. The creation of a graphic identity requires artistic creation to give meaning to the project. We need to go back to the fundamentals, the objectives and the challenges, and try to transpose these into an identity. An initial sketch was drawn up by the project leaders during the application process and then reworked by the Bastille communications agency to finalise the creative work.

1.1. THE LOGO

Figure 1: SOLVE logo.

The SOLVE logo is inspired by the shape of a battery, with the 'E' evoking the charge level of the battery. The logo is subject to certain rules of use to ensure that it is legible and recognizable explained below:

1.2. COLOUR VARIATIONS

Use in colour on a light background. Preferred version of the logo.

Use in white and colour on a dark background. Preferred version of the logo.

White monochrome on a dark background.
Version of the logo to be used only if the white and colour versions are not legible.

Monochrome black on light background.
This version should only be used for black and white documents.

Figure 2: Background colour preferences for SOLVE logo.

To ensure that the logo can be identified quickly on all media, the colour combinations of the logo are limited to the configurations identified above. The emphasis is always on maximum legibility.

1.3. THE PROTECION ZONE

Figure 3: Protection zone for SOLVE logo.

The logotype is protected by an area where no other elements may appear.
This zone corresponds to the 'O' in the logotype.

1.4. MINIMUM SIZE

Figure 4: Minimum size for SOLVE logo.

Web: 45 px
Print: 15 mm

A minimum size is imposed to ensure that the information in the logotype is easy to read.

1.5. RULES OF USE

Use the right logo on a background that makes it legible.

Do not use the logo on a background that does not contrast with its colour.

⊗ Do not use the logo on a background that does not contrast with its colour.

Figure 5: Rules of use for SOLVE logo background.

The logo may be used on photographs, provided that it is perfectly legible.

1.6. PROHIBITIONS

Figure 6: Prohibitions for SOLVE logo.

In general, it is forbidden to modify the appearance of the logotype.

1.7. POSITIONING THE LOGO

Figure 7: Format: A4 (portrait) and homothetic (Size 1).

Size 1 - recommended for posters and document covers.

All communication documents are subject to layout rules that define the margins and size of the logo according to the different formats of the documents.

To ensure consistency in the deployment of the identity, the logo must always be left-aligned.

Figure 8: Format: A4 (portrait) and homothetic (Size 2).

Size 2 - recommended for media with a lot of content.

All communication documents are subject to layout rules that define the margins and size of the logo according to the different formats of the documents.

To ensure consistency in the deployment of the identity, the logo must always be left-aligned.

Figure 9: Format: A4 (landscape) and homothetic (size 1).

Size 1 – recommended for posters and document covers.

All communication documents are subject to layout rules that allow the margins and size of the logotype to be defined according to the different formats of the documents.

To ensure consistency in the deployment of the identity, the logo must always be left-aligned.

Figure 10: Format: A4 (landscape) and homethic (size 2).

Size 2 - recommended for media with a lot of content.

All communication documents are subject to layout rules that allow the margins and size of the logotype to be defined according to the different formats of the documents.

To ensure consistency in the deployment of the identity, the logo must always be left-aligned.

Figure 11: Format: kakemono, 85 x 200 cm.

All communication documents are subject to layout rules that allow the margins and size of the logo to be defined according to the different formats of the documents.

To ensure consistency in the deployment of the identity, the logo must always be left-aligned.

2. LEGAL OBLIGATIONS

Here we look at the legal obligations specific to European projects, with instructions on how to use the logo and the legal environment surrounding it.

2.1. VISIBILITY — EUROPEAN FLAG AND FUNDING STATEMENT

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

Figure 12: Co-funded European Union logos preferences.

Figure 13: Funded European Union logos preferences.

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Figure 14: Protection area.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

For more information about the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programs 2021-2027, please refer to the references at the end of this document.

2.2. QUALITY OF INFORMATION — DISCLAIMER

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3. THE GRAPHIC UNIVERSE

Once the identity has been created, the next step is to create a graphic environment around it. The aim is to bring the identity to life, to give it meaning, thanks to the elements that surround it.

3.1. TYPOGRAPHY

Fractul

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789**

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Figure 15: Fractul typography.

Arial

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789**

Figure 16: Arial typography.

3.2. COLOURS

Figure 17: charter colours.

A palette of colours has been defined for SOLVE's visual identity. This limited selection makes it easier to identify and remember the 'brand'. The combination of colours must always ensure good legibility.

3.3. SHAPES

Figure 18: Charter shapes.

Shapes have been designed for the brand. They are inspired by electrical diagrams.

3.4. ICONOGRAPHY

Figure 19: Examples of photos.

The photographs should highlight the expertise of the employees. People should preferably be photographed on the spot. They should express serenity, authenticity and know-how.

All photos used in the project must come from an image bank whose use is authorised. The copyright must figure on the communication tools. If the illustrations do not come from a personal image bank, it will be necessary to pay the rights of use.

Figure 20: Two-colour photographic.

Two-colour photographic processing may be used. Only the colours in the charter may be used.

4. SOME EXAMPLES OF USE

Figure 21: Stationery.

Figure 22: Press release.

SOLVE
All will be solid.

Title of the presentation
Date

Funded by the European Union

Contents

- 01 Chapter title, level 1
 - Subtitle 1, level 2
 - Subtitle 2
 - Subtitle 3
 - Subtitle 4
- 02 Chapter title, level 1
 - Subtitle 1, level 2
 - Subtitle 2
 - Subtitle 3
 - Subtitle 4
- 03 Chapter title, level 1
 - Subtitle 1, level 2
 - Subtitle 2
 - Subtitle 3
 - Subtitle 4
- 04 Chapter title, level 1
 - Subtitle 1, level 2
 - Subtitle 2
 - Subtitle 3
 - Subtitle 4

SOLVE

Slide title with **framed word**

Title level 1
Title level 2
Current text, level 3
Bulleted list, level 4
Bulleted list, level 5

Automatic text formatting
In a space reserved for text, to change the level of a paragraph and therefore its style (see levels above):
 ◊ [Home] tab,
 ◊ Click on the "Increase list level" icon to move to the next level/style,
 ◊ Click on the "Reduce list level" icon to return to the previous level/style.

Title level 2
Current text, level 3

Chapter 1 - Chapter title (manual bolding)

Slide title with **framed word**

Title level 1
Title level 2
Current text, level 3
Bulleted list, level 4
Bulleted list, level 5

Automatic text formatting
In a space reserved for text, to change the level of a paragraph and therefore its style (see levels above):
 ◊ [Home] tab,
 ◊ Click on the "Increase list level" icon to move to the next level/style,
 ◊ Click on the "Reduce list level" icon to return to the previous level/style.

Chapter 1 - Chapter title (manual bolding)

Agenda

	June	July	August	September	October
Task or activity 1	Details, dates				
Task or activity 2		Details, dates			
Task or activity 3			Details, dates		
Task or activity 4				Details, dates	
Task or activity 5					Details, dates

Chapter 1 - Chapter title (manual bolding)

Thank you !

Contact us
First name Last name
00 00 00 00
quentin.morel@tenerdis.fr

SOLVE

Figure 23: Power point presentations.

5. THE WEBSITE

The website is one of the project's most important communication tools. Its purpose is to present the project to outsiders, to explain its background and objectives, to introduce each member of the consortium and to disseminate all the results of the project.

It must therefore be able to report on the progress of the project and pass on all the information, news and events that are useful for its development. The website is responsive and will automatically adapt to mobile format.

It is scheduled to go online on 31 August 2024, after validation by the communication leader, the coordinator and each member of the consortium. The website URL can be found in the references at the end of the document.

5.1. THE MOCK-UP

Figure 24: Website homepage.

Figure 25: Website news.

Figure 26: Website results.

Figure 27: Website footer.

The photographs in this document and those of the website are still preliminary and do not necessarily reflect the final rendering.

5.2. THE DIFFERENT SECTIONS

5.2.1. THE HOME PAGE

The home page is expected to highlight the latest news, give details of the project's objectives and present the members of the consortium on a map of Europe.

5.2.2. PROJECT

This section will outline the different objectives and challenges of the project at each stage of the value chain.

5.2.3. CONSORTIUM

In this section, all the members of the consortium will be presented, indicating their location in Europe and the stage in the value chain in which they are involved. A link to their website and LinkedIn page will also be displayed.

5.2.4. NEWS

All news and/or events will be published on this page. A filtering system will make it easy to find the content you are looking for (by type of news and by value chain theme).

5.2.5. RESULTS

This section will contain all the deliverables.

5.2.6. CONTACT

A contact form will be available on this page, with a number of fields to fill in, so that you can easily identify the needs.

5.2.7. RESOURCES

In the resources section, you will be able to find information documents, reports, studies, scientific publications, press releases, newsletters and feedback on events, as well as deliverables, which will also be available here in addition to the dedicated section. A filtering system will make it easy to find the information you are looking for.

The website will also feature a search bar, a newsletter subscription form and various links to social networks.

6. SOCIAL MEDIA

The SOLVE project is expected to offer 3 social networks:

- **LinkedIn:** to disseminate information to a professional and scientific audience,
- **X:** to disseminate information to journalists and public authorities,
- **YouTube:** for the video formats that will feed the website and networks.

Access URL can be found in the references at the end of the document.

6.1. LINKEDIN

The LinkedIn account must relay the progress of the project intended for an expert, scientific and professional audience. Scientific publications can in particular be relayed there. LinkedIn is a network that highlights expertise and content intended to provide information that can be useful and fuel the debate on ideas. Interactions will be very important and all outside ideas welcome.

The tone must remain serious, even if it is possible to offer slightly offbeat content to perform.

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile page for the SOLVE project. At the top, there is a banner with logos of various partners: cidetec, PIPISTREL, C22, ACCUREC, ARKEMA, delfort, Fraunhofer IKTS, STELLANTIS, LOMARTOV, PULSEDEON, œerlikon, Politecnico di Torino, SAFT, Tenerrdis, Empa, Tampere University, and the European Union. Below the banner is the SOLVE logo and the project name 'SOLVE'. The description reads: 'Safe Efficient Battery System Based on Advanced Cell Technology. Funded by European Union.' It also indicates 'Services de recherche · 121 abonnés · 11-50 employés'. There is a notification that 'Flavie et 12 autres relations suivent cette page'. Below this are buttons for 'Envoyer un message', 'Suivi', and a menu icon. A navigation bar at the bottom includes 'Accueil', 'À propos', 'Posts', 'Emplois', and 'Personnes'. The 'Infos' section starts with the text: 'This Horizon Europe project aims to develop the next generation of solid-state batteries and deploy them on a large scale in Europe. This 4-year project is led by a consortium of 16 players from several European'.

Figure 28: The LinkedIn page.

SOLVE
121 abonnés
1 mois • Modifié •

SOLVE project off to a flying start! 🚀 This week in #Donostia - #SanSebastian, the #HorizonEurope project consortium met for the first time. The kick-off meeting was hosted by the project coordinator Fundación CIDETEC. ... plus

[Voir la traduction](#)

👍❤️ Elodie Chêne et 69 autres personnes 3 commentaires • 17 replications

SOLVE a republié ceci

BEPA - Batteries European Partnership Association
7 008 abonnés
4 sem. •

! New project !

SOLVE just hosted its kick-off meeting in San Sebastian, where the promising consortium of 16 companies, co-ordinated by CIDETEC, will begin this 4 year EU funded #project.

The project will try to overcome the main challenges in the deployment of Gen4b solid state batteries by focusing on higher performance and improved safety of solid state batteries as well as developing sustainable advanced materials, in line with the EU #battery Regulation.

Learn more by checking out their press release https://lnkd.in/d7_pv3qV

CIDETEC | Saft | Arkema | Centro Ricerche Fiat | Pipistrel Vertical Solutions | CEA | Pulsedion | ACCUREC-Recycling GmbH - | delfort | Politecnico di Torino | Tampere University | Fraunhofer IKTS | Empa - Structural Engineering Research Laboratory | Oerlikon | LOMARTOV SL | Tenerrdis

[Voir la traduction](#)

SOLVE

👍❤️ Andriy Kvasha et 34 autres personnes 5 replications

Figure 29: Examples of posts.

6.2. X

The X page will make it possible to address the media world (journalists) and public authorities, who could act as powerful relays for the project. The publications will be rarer than on LinkedIn but we will highlight the most important information, the major progress of the project illustrated by press releases, likely to interest the media.

Figure 30: The X page.

6.3. YOUTUBE

The YouTube page should really serve as a support for other networks. Presentation videos from the consortium partners and more technical interviews on the progress of the project will be published there. The videos may be published in an offbeat tone or not. To increase the performance of posts on social networks, it is strongly recommended to use fairly short video formats (2 min max) in order to keep the audience captivated on the videos until the end.

The YouTube shorts model (10-30 seconds long videos in portrait mobile screen format) can also be used to boost performance.

All video packaging will be produced by the project's communications agency: Bastille.

Figure 31: The YouTube page.

CONCLUSIONS

This document aims to serve as a compass for all members of the SOLVE consortium on how to use the project's graphic charter. It is essential to respect the brand identity to maximize the power of the communication and dissemination.

The project's communication leader is available to help consortium members with any communication-related queries. Similarly, if the members of the consortium wish to make corrections or comments on the content of the various communication tools (website, posts on social networks, etc.), they are free to inform the communication leader via a private channel (e-mail, video, phone call).

Any element published as part of the project must absolutely contain the legal obligations relating to the European Union (logo, disclaimer and specific notices) as mentioned on the page 14.

The various existing document models and communication tools are already available to the members of the consortium.

ANNEX 1: COMMUNICATION PRODUCTION TIMELINE

Figure 32: Communication production timeline.

Funded by the European Union (Grant n°.101147094) Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority (CINEA) can be held responsible for them.

ANNEX 2: REFERENCES

The following references included below are helpful to answer any query related to this deliverable:

1. The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programs 2021-2027 (pdf):

https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/3192a0ef-6bda-4e1a-81ca-65ade2ffad73_en?filename=eu_emblem_rules.pdf

2. Link to download the logos:

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

3. Site web link:

<http://www.solveproject.eu/>

1. LinkedIn page link:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/solveproject/?viewAsMember=true>

2. X page link:

<https://x.com/SOLVEprojectEU>

3. YouTube page link:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdPaxiEAqJxENTQF6bVGAhg>